

LIVING A LIFE: THE CHALLENGES OF SOCIAL WORKERS IN RURAL COMMUNITIES OF LEBAK, SULTAN KUDARAT

Elen May R. Pascua, Rondick O. Piodos, Rhejaen B. Pellen

Goldenstate College of Koronadal City, City of Koronadal, South Cotabato, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study described the challenges of social workers in rural communities. Through the use of phenomenological research design, four (4) registered social workers (RSWs) working in Lebak, Sultan Kudarat were interviewed via online conferencing platform (Zoom). The participants shared their personal and professional experiences in working with rural communities. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis: transcription, codings into clustered themes, and emergent themes. The qualitative results highlighted that difficult geographical location and attitudes and behaviors of community people are the main challenges that the participants experienced. Moreover, they also shared that they deal with those challenges through professionalism and good communication. Additionally, this study highlights participatory approach as their strategy for intervention as the community people are actively involved in the planning and implementation of government's programs and services.

Keywords: *Social work, rural social work, rural communities, participatory approach, challenges*

INTRODUCTION

In nature, social work practitioners improve and enhance the lives of the oppressed and vulnerable individuals, groups, and communities. They are the key players in human development and social welfare. Rural communities are one of the fields of social work

practitioners that have several experiences of oppression and vulnerability (Pawar, 2014). Social workers in rural communities are said to have remained in their positions for a longer period of time. They also have greater autonomy and decision-making authority, support and fairness for professional growth than social workers in urban and larger institutions. There are studies stating that rural social workers receive more respect from the community leaders—they usually live in the community and are known and trusted. Rural workers are engaged in using informal networks, and they can sometimes make use of informal resources and relationship skills to create tailored resources suitable for their clientele system (Brown et al., 2017).

According to international studies, rural communities can span from the less-populated towns outside of large and small city centers to remote areas in the mountains, plains, and deserts across the nation. Social issues like high levels of poverty (United States Department of Agriculture, 2018); limited access to healthcare (Health Resources and Services Administration, 2017; Rural Health Information Hub, 2017); disparities in physical and mental health support; rising crime; an increase in child and woman abuse and neglect (Administration for Children and Families, 2010); and limited educational resources are just a few of the issues faced by rural communities.

Thus, the need for social workers is more prevalent in these kinds of communities. Due to rising social inequality and limited access to services in rural areas, the need for social work in rural communities may be greater than it was in the past (Ginsberg, 2014). The World Bank Group initiated the Philippine Rural Development Project targeting 750,000 beneficiaries in the whole country which aims to reduce poverty and increase productivity, income and employment. People living in the rural communities like farmers and fisher folks have always suffered from “low incomes, limited access to the use of resources like farm machinery, production inputs and technology, agricultural assets and services, poor access to market, and impact of weather events like typhoons”.

Pal (1959) of Siliman University defined rural sociology as social groups who are living in “towns”. These are known to have small and simple institutions that make up a community of people with their own identity, social control, folkways, and mores. Traced from the Spanish regime in the Philippines, a poblacion and ten (10) to twenty-five (25) barrios (now called a Barangay) make up a town. Agriculture and fishing are the most common occupations in a town. The transportation before was to travel on foot or on a carabao’s back. Every town has its dialect, ideas and values which incorporates a diverse Filipino culture today. As indicated in the 2020 Philippine Statistics Authority, Urban Population and Housing Census, the Philippines has fifty-four percent (54%) Filipinos living in urban societies, while forty-six (46%) are living in rural communities. Social workers use a generalist approach in dealing with the Philippines’ individuals, groups, families, and communities.

This research study aims to acknowledge the need in understanding the complexity of providing “an ethical, responsive and appropriate service in rural areas”. It is a challenge for social workers working in far-flung areas because of different obstacles in transportation, technology, and even culture which impacts both their personal and

professional roles (Wurzweiler School of Social Work, 2020). Whether in rural or urban communities, there are minimal local studies regarding the approaches, challenges, and gaps of social workers in rural communities (Landsman and Rathman, 2023). There are distinct conditions in rural communities from urban contexts, and there is a call upon social welfare to become aware of the differences in methods that are effective in mainstream social work, which are ineffective for rural societies (Agents of Change). This is to customize helping approaches and social work methodologies deemed appropriate for remote clientele groups.

Research Questions

1. What are the challenges social workers face while delivering services in rural communities?
2. How do social workers deal with the challenges they face in working with rural communities?
3. What approaches or strategies do social workers use as interventions in working with rural communities?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed phenomenology as research design to describe the experiences of social workers working with rural communities. According to Carl Moustakas (1994), phenomenology is an approach to studying and understanding human experiences and exploring how people perceive phenomena. It seeks to provide a description rather than an explanation by starting from a free perspective where a distinct situation or phenomenon brings the individual's situation, perceptions, and experiences but does not turn into a direct generalization.

Locale of the Study

The researchers conducted the study at Lebak, Sultan Kudarat. Lebak is a first-class municipality in Sultan Kudarat with a land area of 470.86 square kilometers. The researchers chose Lebak due to its rugged landscape and isolated highland areas contribute to a mostly rural lifestyle, with many communities spread across its extensive mountain ranges and valleys that make it mountainous and highly rural setting.

Lebak has 27 barangays; four (4) are identified rural communities: Villamonte, Kalamungog, Datu Karon, and Kaytodak. These Barangays are identified because of their geographical location, which is twenty (20) kilometres away from the center of the Municipality of Lebak.

Research Participants

The participants of this study were four (4) Registered Social Workers assigned at Lebak, Sultan Kudarat, through the use of purposive sampling method. The participants were identified purposely through the following inclusion criteria: First, the participants must be professional social workers with valid licenses; Second, they must be working at least one (1) year in a rural community in Lebak; Third, they are currently assigned in Lebak, Sultan Kudarat; Fourth, they must have direct involvement in addressing community challenges such as poverty alleviation, family welfare, or youth rehabilitation in rural areas; And fifth, they must agree to the conduct of the study with approved informed consent letter. This specific focus on social workers stationed in Lebak ensured that the study captures the experiences of those deeply familiar with the rural communities and their unique social, economic, and cultural dynamics.

Research Instrument

In this study, Key Informant Interview (KII) interviews were conducted to gather data and researcher-made semi-structured interview guide was used. Semi-structured interviews delve into topics you have previously determined are pertinent to the study. A generic list of themes, which may contain structured and open-ended questions, can be used as a starting point for semi-structured interview planning (Johnston and Longhurst, 2023).

The semi-structured interview guide were composed of open-ended questions that helped answer the research questions. The interview guide were validated by three (3) qualified validators prior to the conduct of the study.

Data Collection

Firstly, the researchers sent invitation letters to the identified participants via email, clearly explaining the purpose of the study and the importance of their insights in this study. An informed consent form was then sent after they have responded to the invitation letter. Afterwards, the researchers scheduled the interviews based on the participants' availability. One-on-one Interviews were conducted through the video conferencing application Zoom. This was agreed by both parties due to the distant location of the participants. The interviews to all participants were audio-recorded.

Analysis of Data

After the interviews, the data gathered, specifically the audio recordings were transcribed. The interview transcriptions were given back to the participants for review and verification. The participants signed a participants' verification form after reviewing the interview transcripts.

Through thematic analysis, the researchers systematically went through each transcript, bracketed important or meaningful sections, assigned a code to each segment that reflects its content, categorized it from specific concepts, and grouped them into broader themes or categories. Those themes presented visually to show the relationship

among emerging themes and codes. Then, the themes reviewed and described accordingly in the context of the experiences of the social workers, their challenges and how they coped with those challenges they face.

RESULTS

The Challenges of Social Workers in Rural Communities

Table 1 presents the challenges of social workers faced while delivering services in rural communities.

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
A. Mode of Transportation to the Community B. Limited Access of Government Facilities	Difficult Geographical Location
A. Attitudes and Characters of Community People	Community Behavioral Traits

Difficult Geographical Location

A. Mode of Transportation

P1/OLYMPUS: “For example, uhm, if your call time in your area is nine o’clock, then most likely, you should leave the municipality at six AM or before six AM because the only means of transportation we use are hired habal-habal or a single motorcycle... So most likely, the challenges are really just the travel time...”

P2/GUENNETH: “So, the distance, especially in the municipality of Lebak, is quite challenging. The case I’m handling involves three barangays, and the biggest hindrance there is the mode of transportation, (external noise from participant) and then the farm-to-market roads...”

P3/JOHN: “The community we’re working with is quite far, so the road we take is, of course, not well-paved. So, one of the problems if you are assigned to a rural area is, of course, the transportation access. That’s one of the biggest challenges, especially since you travel it every day.”

P4/FRANCIS: “When we go to the community, it’s quite difficult to access in terms of transportation. So, the challenge there is, first, the physical aspect of working with the community in a rural area. Because you’re more prone to exhaustion when you’re in a rural community, mainly because of transportation.”

B. Limited Access of Government Facilities

P2/GUENNETH: "...Our main focus is to help the rural and remote areas, so they are the ones who really need our assistance, mostly the people in the community, right? They are the ones who, uhm, need more attention, services, and... our sincerity in helping them. So that's the main focus, right there."

P3/JOHN: "Of course, the facilities built in the community are limited because, as mentioned, it's far. So that's also one of the problems I encounter when working in rural communities, especially in Lebak."

Community Behavioral Traits

A. Attitudes and Characters of Community People

P4/FRANCIS: "...we are strangers when we first meet the community where we work, so (pause) We are strangers, so we also need to adjust to the attitudes and character of the people living in the community. This means we have to adjust because when we get there, the culture, attitudes, and behaviors of the people are different, especially the people in rural communities. Because, you know, we come from, some of us, commonly, come from the city, and eventually, we get assigned to rural communities, so we have to adjust in terms of the character of the people we work with."

How Social Workers Deak with Rural Communities

Table 2 presents how social workers deal with the challenges in working with working in rural communities.

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
A. Controlled Emotional Involvement in Dealing with People B. Self-Determination of the People C. Optimism of a Social Worker D. Being Resilient as a Social Worker	Professionalism as a Social Worker
A. Coordination with Stakeholders B. Proper Communication with the People and the Agency	Good Communication Skills

<p>C. Building Strong Rapport and Good Relationship with Community</p>	
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Professionalism as a Social Worker

A. Controlled Emotional Involvement in Dealing with People

P1/OLYMPUS: "...We are bounded by the social work code of conduct and ethics (pause). So, the controlled emotional involvement in dealing with your clients or beneficiaries because, in the circumstances that you are weak or you get too emotionally involved in their struggles in life, such as poverty, you will not be an effective worker. So, we still anchor ourselves on our (pause) social work principles, which we must always carry with us when delivering services to the clientele or the beneficiaries themselves..."

B. Self-Determination of the People

P2/GUENNETH: "Self-determination, real determination, that if this is my goal, I will help them uplift their lives, even if it's not a hundred percent, even if it's fifty percent or thirty percent of their lives. Self-determination and also inner strength, standing firm in yourself."

C. Optimism of a Social Worker

P3/JOHN: "...So, we really just have to be optimistic about what we're doing and always stay positive. Then, uhm, I also think that this is for the betterment of the people there. Because we only live once, so why not help other people, especially those in marginalized communities or in Lebak."

D. Being Resilient as a Social Worker

P4/FRANCIS: "In dealing with those challenges, we just need to be resilient as social workers. If we're having difficulty in terms of transportation, we need to adjust, physically get up early, prepare early so we can be on time when we arrive at the community. Those are the physical sacrifices we need to make. And then, in terms of dealing with their attitudes in the community, we remain professional. We are trained on how to adjust and how to better deal with different kinds of people, especially those in rural areas."

Good Communication Skills

A. Coordination with Stakeholders

P1/OLYMPUS: "Coordination really matters. Because when you're working with different communities or different stakeholders, your coordination should always be a

priority. If you don't have the skill for proper coordination, most likely, there will be problems with the program you're implementing in that area."

P2/GUENNETH: "Uhm, for example, uhm, in my case, the biggest struggle I faced was that I had an accident while I was in the area. Although I was physically injured and couldn't go to the area, we still have modes of communication to connect or find other ways to ask for help, even from other members of DSWD, because they need assistance. Through communication. Proper communication is really important."

B. Proper Communication with the People and Agency

P3/JOHN: "They are the ones providing good programs for the betterment of the community there. So, of course, their role is very important because the budget to implement those programs or interventions comes from them, which are formulated with the community people. Also, by giving their full support to the programs or interventions created by the community to achieve their community goals, the full support of the LGU is also one of the biggest roles of the LGU to overcome the challenges."

C. Building Strong Rapport and Good Relationship with the Community

P4/FRANCIS: "As social workers, it's important to really build a strong rapport with the community people. We need to be good at or able to build a good relationship with the community leaders, especially the officials in the barangay, and then the purok leaders. It's important that we build rapport or relationships with them so that, in that regard, we can help each other, and they can also assist us with the challenges we face every day while working with the entire community."

Approaches and Strategies of Social Workers

Table 3 presents the approaches and strategies of social workers used as interventions in working with rural communities.

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
<p>A. Letting the People Identify their Needs</p> <p>B. Community Awareness as an Approach</p> <p>C. Building Strong Rapport and Resiliency</p>	<p>Participatory Approach</p>

Participatory Approach

A. Letting the People Identify their Needs

P1/OLYMPUS: "...We assess and assist (emphasized tone of voice) the clients or beneficiaries whose social functioning is somewhat weak. We help them by identifying what resources are available to them, and then we enhance those resources if that's what they want to happen in their lives."

P2/GUENNETH: "Ah, that's, uhm, based on my experience, the participatory approach. Everything you do in the community needs the participation of everyone. As a worker, you really have to involve the whole community. For example, if you're organizing a group, they decide what their needs are, they come up with the solutions, and we just guide them. It's really all about being participatory."

P3/JOHN: "...The majority decision of the people should be followed, because that way, there won't be any problems where it's not just you, as a social worker, solving the problem and deciding what they want. As a social worker or leader in the community, you also give them the ability for self-determination, meaning you give them the chance to make decisions for themselves."

B. Community Awareness as an Approach

P3/JOHN: "...So, promoting community awareness is one of the best approaches for the community in Lebak because many people there, especially in the barangay I was assigned to, are not yet aware or open-minded about the help the government can provide, especially from the LGU of Lebak, to address the issues or current problems they are facing. Then, there's also active involvement. One of the good approaches to apply there is the active involvement of the community people in formulating solutions or interventions. Because they are the ones who are truly your partners in implementing the programs you are doing there."

C. Building Strong Rapport and Resiliency

P4/FRANCIS: "So, uhm, we have many approaches and techniques in terms of social work knowledge, but in layman's terms, the strategies we commonly use are building a strong rapport or relationship with key people in the community, such as parent leaders, purok leaders, and barangay officials. So, the most important thing is building a good rapport with the people we work with in the community. Then second, we need to be resilient as social workers. There are many adversities and challenges when working in rural communities, but as a social worker, we need to be resilient. We must have a good resolve to face any problems that come our way."

DISCUSSION

The Challenges of Social Workers in Rural Communities

This study described the challenges of the social workers in rural communities of based on the interview conducted on four (4) social workers assigned in Lebak, Sultan Kudarat. The main challenge was the difficult geographical location of the rural communities. All of the participants answered that the physical aspect of the community caused some challenges like delayed community meetings or assemblies and missed appointments due to the demanding time to travel and the difficulty in obtaining transportation due to undeveloped road networks. Also, according to the gathered data by the researchers, people in rural communities need more attention and interventions.

People in the rural communities are vulnerable to health insurance coverage, and other government amenities and educational facilities. Data shows that rural poverty is a multifaceted problem driven by economic systems, accessibility issues, and historical inequities. To address these inequities, focused policies, such as expenditures in education, healthcare, infrastructure, and job development, must be developed in accordance with the specific needs of rural communities. (Kane, 2024).

According to IFAD (2023), More than half of the Philippines' 113 million inhabitants live in rural areas, and 36% of them are impoverished, relying on agriculture as their primary and often sole source of revenue. Poverty levels differ significantly across regions and provinces, and the disparity between urban and rural areas is expanding. Indigenous people living in highly fragile and vulnerable ecosystems in Mindanao's uplands and highlands, as well as farmers and fishers in disaster-prone coastal areas and Mindanao Island conflict zones, are among the poorest in the country. These data highlight the ongoing difficulty of rural poverty in the Philippines, which is driven by factors such as fewer economic possibilities, poorer educational attainment, and inadequate access to key services in rural regions. This challenges requires focused policies and investments to improve rural infrastructure, education, and healthcare access, with the goal of lowering poverty rates and promoting economic well-being for all communities.

The social work strategies in rural development are primarily concerned with to enable individuals and communities to use their natural abilities and resources. It is important to understand their different innate attitudes and behaviors as they have their unique culture as their identity. The importance of social work initiatives in improving lives in rural regions cannot be emphasized. Rural populations are not monolithic; they vary in culture, geography, and socioeconomic status. As a result, effective social work interventions must be adapted to the specific characteristics and challenges of each rural community. This necessitates a thorough awareness of their local circumstances and close collaboration with community people to identify the individual needs and gaps to be able to formulate interventive measures as their aspirations in life (Reddy, 2023).

How Social Workers Deal with Rural Communities

The findings in this study explains that despite the external challenges that the social workers experience as they work in rural communities, they always maintain professionalism by employing the knowledge and skills of their profession into real and direct practice, and by proper coordination to the local stakeholders to strengthen the support and augment the needs of the people in the communities.

The social workers in the Philippines need a wide range of abilities to effectively address complex social issues and contribute to the well-being of individuals and communities. Effective rural practice frequently involves locality-based community development which may render professional distance or boundaries that are undesirable and can limit efficacy. This is why protecting clients from the harmful repercussions of dual partnerships in rural settings requires competent management of professional connections rather than imposing obvious boundaries. Many rural areas share tight communal ties, which could be a great strength in empowerment and development (Daley, 2015).

According to the Institute of Social Works & Research (2023), social workers play an important role in uplifting underprivileged groups. They accomplish this by developing and implementing initiatives that promote social fairness, increase economic opportunity, and address systemic hurdles. Social workers act as advocates for these disadvantaged populations, ensuring that they have a say in decisions and access to basic resources like education, healthcare, and livelihood programs. Social workers facilitate collaboration across government agencies, non-governmental groups, and local communities to build long-term solutions that empower individuals to break the cycle of poverty and social exclusion. Their efforts not only meet immediate needs, but also foster long-term resilience in communities, allowing them to become self-sufficient and actively contribute in their own development.

This study also highlighted collaboration with a wide range of stakeholders, including government and non-governmental agencies, as well as community-based organizations, is critical to social work success. Empowerment and strengths-based approaches are important, concentrating on assisting individuals and communities in capitalizing on their current assets and resilience to achieve long-term good change. Overall, social work practices are dynamic and adaptive, designed to meet the specific needs and settings of the individuals and communities they serve (Reddy, 2023). Building rapport and making genuine connections are critical in social work, especially in community development, since they lay the groundwork for efficient service delivery. When social workers build trust and strong interpersonal ties with community members, they foster an environment in which people feel comfortable discussing their worries and needs. This trust is essential for overcoming skepticism and resistance to foreign interventions, which are typical in marginalized or rural populations. A strong connection enables social workers to obtain a greater understanding of the community's cultural dynamics, traditions, and special difficulties, allowing them to create more relevant and sustainable programs. The strength of these relationships has a direct impact on the

effectiveness of interventions, as engaged and empowered communities are more likely to participate in and support social programs (Starks, et. al., 2016).

Approaches and Strategies of Social Workers

This study emphasized the Participatory Approach as the strategy of social workers to develop intervention plan for the families and members of rural communities. Research on the challenges of social workers in rural communities highlights that top-down interventions often face resistance due to deeply rooted traditions, mistrust of external aid, and lack of awareness about available resources. Social workers in this study stated that promoting local people to be involved in decision making can affect their personal and communal lives as they are more involved in the planning and program implementation.

The participatory approach is a transformative method for development research which prioritize the active participation and empowerment of farmers in the development process. It turns the attention away from external actors and toward community members themselves, transforming them from passive recipients to active participants. The participatory approach to applied anthropology reflects a paradigm shift in how we see and carry out development projects. By putting community members at the center of their growth, through recognizing their needs and wants, we recognize their expertise, respect their agency, and lay the road for long-term transformation. This also promotes sustainability as they take part on the planning process and improves active participation as the implementation of the program occur (Kumar, 2023).

According to Live To Plant (2025), Accountability and openness are enhanced when the community is involved in impact monitoring and assessment. Participatory Approach empowers locals to examine their own conditions and express their observations about project-related improvements. Engaging local communities throughout the project cycle, from planning to evaluation, ensures that efforts are relevant and responsive to current needs. Encouraging engagement increases community members' ownership and commitment. Investing in capacity-building for local institutions improves their ability to effectively manage development programs. Communities can be empowered through training programs in leadership development, financial literacy, and technical skills. Partnerships between local groups, government agencies, NGOs, and corporate sector actors foster synergies that improve resource mobilization and project design through diversified expertise.

Conclusions

Social workers in rural areas face significant challenges, primarily due to difficult geographical conditions and the behaviors and attitudes of community members that may conflict with professional ethics. These factors hinder the delivery of essential services and often result in transportation issues, delays, and financial burdens. The lack of accessible infrastructure and government services deepens rural poverty and underscores the need for targeted interventions and policies that address the unique socio-economic barriers of these communities.

To address these challenges, social workers rely on professionalism, effective communication, and the application of social work principles. They adapt to local norms and cultures, establish rapport, and build trust with community members through direct engagement and interpersonal skills. Collaboration with stakeholders such as barangay officials and local government units also plays a key role in achieving effective and respectful service delivery, reinforcing the credibility and value of their work in rural settings.

A participatory approach is a key strategy used by social workers in rural communities, involving stakeholders in every phase of intervention planning and implementation. This method fosters empowerment, community ownership, and collaborative problem-solving. By encouraging residents to identify their own needs and participate actively in decision-making, social workers not only enhance community awareness and resilience but also strengthen the overall impact and sustainability of their interventions.

Recommendations

Given the unique challenges faced by social workers in rural communities, it is recommended that government agencies and social work institutions develop more context-sensitive policies and programs that address geographical barriers and cultural differences. Providing transportation allowances, improving access to remote areas, and building local infrastructure can help ease logistical burdens. Social workers should continue to enhance their cultural competence and communication skills to effectively engage with diverse populations. Capacity-building programs and regular professional development training should be implemented to equip social workers with adaptive strategies and emotional resilience necessary for rural assignments. Moreover, strengthening partnerships with local government units, non-government organizations, and community stakeholders is vital in ensuring the sustainability and effectiveness of social interventions.

Future studies could expand the scope by including a larger and more diverse sample of social workers from various rural regions to gain a broader understanding of their challenges and coping strategies. Comparative studies between urban and rural social work practice may also provide insights into systemic disparities and possible solutions. Additionally, further research can explore the long-term outcomes of participatory approaches in rural community development, as well as the role of technology in improving service delivery in remote areas. Investigating the perspectives of community members themselves could also offer valuable input in shaping more inclusive and effective social work practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study aims to uphold ethical considerations that respect and empower social workers who generously share their experiences through the informed consent form, which explains confidentiality, cultural sensitivity, and transparency. Before the interview, the participants were given a clear explanation about why the research is being done,

how it is carried out, any possible dangers, and the advantages and risks. They should join of their own freewill, without coercion or pressure, and they should know they can withdraw their participation whenever they want without facing any consequences.

The study also used code names for each participant to keep their identity private and protect confidential information about their clients or community. The researchers remained sensitive in language use, may it be in gender or cultural dynamics and allow the participants to skip any questions they find uncomfortable to avoid inflicting harm or emotional distress on them. The researchers informed participants about how their data will be utilized. This includes using their insights for research publications, social work practices, or policy recommendations. Participants are also allowed to review or confirm the study findings to ensure their perspectives are accurately shown. Member-checking, also called this approach, improves the credibility and ethical validity of the research.

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